

PHOENICIAN SEEDS ARE RICH IN MINERALS: A MULTI-ANALYTICAL STUDY OF MINERALISED ARCHAEOBOTANICAL REMAINS FROM THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE OF MOTYA

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ARCHAEOLOGICAL CONTEXT

- Motya – 40 ha island on the western coast of Sicily (Marsala lagoon)
- Subject of excavations by Sapienza University of Rome since 1964
- Temple of Cappiddazzu – one of the two major temples of Motya, probably dedicated to Melqart/Herakles
- Archaeobotanical sampling and processing of a deep pit (*favissa*) used for discharging votive material, especially remains of food offerings and sacrificed animals

MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS:

- Individuation of characteristic morphological features
- Identification of Euphorbiaceae, Lamiaceae and Boraginaceae
- Comparison with analogues from herbarium collections

IN PROGRESS:

- Curve fit for determination of silica structure
- Coupling with XRD analysis to complete characterization

DRIFT FTIR:

- Whole-sample composition
- Formation of opal silica (S, biosilicification) in both/either moderna and/or archaeological samples
- Clear identification of aragonite
- Variation of organic matter (mineralization)

SPECULAR REFLECTANCE FTIR:

- Information about surface composition
- Determination of kaolinite (K) in most the samples (hypothesis of replacement mineralisation)
- Calcite (C) and aragonite (A) combination
- Variation in organic matter (OM) content

Outer-Surface

Cross-Section

SEM-EDX ANALYSIS:

- Comparison of surface and cross-section morphology and composition between modern and archaeological analogues
- Differences in spatial distribution of characteristic elements by SEM-EDX mapping
- Individuation of biomineralization processes, particularly biosilicification, for some modern samples